

Simultaneous determination of dextromethorphan and pseudoephedrine in cough syrup formulations using net analyte signal concept

Reza Hajian^{a*} and Hadiss Izadi^b

^aYoung Researchers Club, Gachsaran Branch, Islamic Azad University, 75818-63876, Gachsaran, Iran
E-mail : hajian@iaug.ac.ir

^bChemistry Department, Gachsaran Branch, Islamic Azad University, 75818-63876, Gachsaran, Iran

Manuscript received online 27 August 2013, accepted 23 September 2013

Abstract : Net analyte signal standard addition method (NASSAM) is presented for the simultaneous determination of dextromethorphan and pseudoephedrine by spectrophotometry. The method combines the advantages of the standard addition method with the net analyte signal concept which enables the extraction of information concerning a certain analyte from spectra of multi-component mixtures. This method has some advantages such as the use of a full spectrum realization in a signal step, therefore, it does not require calibration and prediction steps and only a few measurements are required for the determination. The simultaneous determination of dextromethorphan and pseudoephedrine was performed in Britton-Robinson buffer (pH 9.0). Two pharmaceutical compounds were determined in concentration ranges of 4.0×10^{-4} – 1.6 mmol L⁻¹ and 4.0×10^{-4} – 0.8 mmol L⁻¹ respectively. The proposed method has been successfully applied to the simultaneous determination of dextromethorphan and pseudoephedrine in some synthetic and pharmaceutical formulations (Dextromethorphan-P syrup).

Keywords : Dextromethorphan, pseudoephedrine, overlapping spectra, net analyte signal, determination.

Introduction

Direct UV-absorbance measurement is subjected to interference from co-formulated drugs, excipients and/or degradation products. Net analyte signal (NAS) is an analytical technique of great utility for extracting quantitative information from spectra composed of unresolved bands. It tends to emphasize subtle spectral features by representing them in a new and visually more accessible way allowing the resolution of multicomponent systems and minimizing the effect of spectral background interferences in pharmaceutical application¹⁻⁷.

Pseudoephedrine (PSU) (2-methylamino-1-phenylpropan-1-ol) is an effective sympathomimetic agent for use as a nasal decongestant with peripheral effects similar to epinephrine and central effects, but less intense than, amphetamines. At the recommended oral dosage, it has little or no pressor effect in normotensive adults. The drug produces fewer adverse effects than ephedrine, specifically, tachycardia, hypertension and central nervous system stimulation⁸. In the past few years, methods based on high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)^{9,10}

and derivative spectrophotometry has been reported for the determination of PSU in biological samples and pharmaceutical preparations¹¹⁻¹³. Most of the mentioned methods are expensive and involve tedious sample pre-treatments.

Dextromethorphan HBr (DEX) (3-methoxy-17-methyl-(9 α ,13 α ,14 α)-morphinan) is a cough suppressant, which has a central action on the cough center in the medulla and is used in the treatment of respiratory disorders¹⁴. Various recent methods including liquid chromatography and HPLC¹⁵⁻¹⁷, derivative spectrophotometry^{18,19} and capillary electrophoresis have been used for the determination of DEX in pharmaceutical preparations and biological fluids²⁰. DEX is a compound that can be present in combination with PSU in cough cold syrups and biological samples. A micellar electrokinetic chromatography (MEKC) based method is among the only proposed method for simultaneous determination of PSU and DEX in capsules²¹.

Spectrophotometric methods of analysis are more economic and simpler, compared to methods such as chro-

matography and electrophoresis. Coupling of these not-expensive methods with chemometrics methods has circumvented the problems from overlap of spectral data and has made it possible to determine a number of desired analytes in many complex samples, without need for tedious pretreatment or separation of interferences.

In this work, a sensitive, selective, accurate and inexpensive procedure for simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of pseudoephedrine and dextromethorphan by using the net analyte signals standard additions method (NASSAM) with simultaneous addition of both analytes was applied. This method is a novel standard addition method based on the net analyte signal (NAS) concept. In this paper, an attempt was made to calculate NAS vectors and attribute them to the analyte concentration using UV-Visible spectrophotometry technique.

Theory :

The net analyte signal (NAS) was defined by Lorber²², based on spectroscopic methods, as the part of the spectrum of a mixture that is unique for the analyte of interest, i.e. it is orthogonal to the spectra of the interferences.

The conventional notation has been used throughout the following discussion. Boldface capital letter is used for a matrix, a boldface lower case for a column vector and lightface lower case italic for a scalar. The superscript T designates the operation of the vector or matrix transposition and the superscript + denotes the pseudo-inverse of a non-square matrix. The digitized spectrum is referred to as a spectrum vector or simply as a vector, while a spectrum vector of a pure component is called a component vector.

Consider a synthetic mixture containing PSU and DEX with the concentrations of 50 and 10 μmol L⁻¹ respectively. The simultaneous determination of two analytes by NASSAM requires having spectrum vector of the mixture. Then several known amounts of PSU and DEX are successively added to the sample solution. The resulting absorbances are measured and expressed by the following equations :

$$A_0 = \epsilon_{\text{PSU}}C_{\text{PSU}}^0 + \epsilon_{\text{DEX}}C_{\text{DEX}}^0 \quad (1)$$

$$A_1 = A_0 + \epsilon_{\text{PSU}}C_{\text{PSU},s_1} + \epsilon_{\text{DEX}}C_{\text{DEX},s_1} \quad (2)$$

$$A_1 = A_{i-1} + \epsilon_{\text{PSU}}C_{\text{PSU},s_i} + \epsilon_{\text{DEX}}C_{\text{DEX},s_i} \quad (3)$$

$$A_n = A_{n-1} + \epsilon_{\text{PSU}}C_{\text{PSU},s_n} + \epsilon_{\text{DEX}}C_{\text{DEX},s_n} \quad (4)$$

where A_0 and A_i are the absorbances of the synthetic mixture before and after of standard additions. C_{PSU}^0 , C_{DEX}^0 are the initial concentrations of PSU and DEX in the sample and C_{PSU,s_i} , C_{DEX,s_i} are the added concentrations of PSU and DEX to the sample in i -th step. Also ϵ_{PSU} and ϵ_{DEX} are molar absorptivities of PSU and DEX respectively.

The NAS vectors for PSU and DEX compounds after each standard addition, $\text{NAS}_{\text{PSU},i}$ and $\text{NAS}_{\text{DEX},i}$ can be found by the following equations respectively :

$$\text{NAS}_{\text{PSU},i} = (I - S^+S)A_i \quad (5)$$

$$\text{NAS}_{\text{DEX},i} = (I - T^+T)A_i \quad (6)$$

where I is an identical matrix, S and T are the matrixes of absorbances in different concentrations of interference (DEX or PSU) respectively according to Tables 1 and 2. By definition, it is always possible to split up the spectrum of a sample (A_i) into two distinct parts for example : NAS_{PSU} which is orthogonal to the spectra of the inter-

Table 1. The concentrations of DEX used for the interference spectra in matrix (S)

	Dextromethorphan (mmol L ⁻¹)		
0.0004	0.060	0.20	0.34
0.0012	0.80	0.22	0.36
0.002	0.10	0.24	0.40
0.004	0.12	0.26	0.60
0.008	0.14	0.28	0.80
0.020	0.16	0.30	1.20
0.040	0.18	0.32	1.60

Table 2. The concentrations of PSE used for the interference spectra in matrix (T)

	Pseudoephedrine (mmol L ⁻¹)		
0.0004	0.10	0.28	1.60
0.0012	0.12	0.30	2.0
0.002	0.14	0.32	2.4
0.004	0.16	0.34	4.0
0.008	0.18	0.36	5.0
0.020	0.20	0.40	6.0
0.040	0.22	0.60	7.0
0.060	0.24	0.80	8.0
0.080	0.26	1.20	

ference (DEX) and S^+SA_i . Where S^+SA_i is a part of the spectrum that is generated by a linear combination of the spectra of the interfering agent. Consequently, S^+SA_i can not be unique for the analyte of interest, because it can also be produced by a mixture of interfering agent. The other part NAS_{PSU} is orthogonal to the spectra of the interference reflecting the part of the spectrum which is only depending on the analyte PSU present in the mixture.

Similar expressions can be used for calculating NAS_{DEX} vector. Therefore the orthogonal vector of PSU and DEX which known as NAS_{PSU} and NAS_{DEX} can be used for quantification of the analytes PSU and DEX respectively. Fig. 1 shows the geometrical presentation of analyte, interferent, mixtures, S^+SA_i and NAS_{PSU} vectors. The shape of NAS_{PSU} only depends on the presence of interference (DEX) in the mixture, not on their specific concentrations and only addition or deletion of components can change NAS_{PSU} .

In binary mixtures when the interferences are known, the NAS can be calculated for the analytes. Norm of the NAS vector can be used to construct a univariate calibration model, where this parameter is plotted against the analyte concentration and a linear relationship is observed. In the case of matrix effect, standard addition plots can be constructed against added standard additions.

Fig. 1. Representation of vector space for analyte (PSU) and interference (DEX) in two dimensional space. NAS vector NAS_{PSU} is different from PSU vector in direction and length.

Experimental

Initial investigation :

To demonstrate the analytical applicability of the proposed method for the analysis of binary mixtures, two pure spectra of PSU and DEX were recorded separately. As it is shown in Fig. 2, the spectra are overlapped in the range of 220–300 nm. Fig. 3 shows successive standard

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of 2.0 mmol L⁻¹ pseudoephedrine and 0.16 mmol L⁻¹ dextromethorphan at pH 9.0.

Fig. 3. The spectra of solution after standard additions of PSU and DEX in the same molar ratios in the concentration range of 10–60 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for spectra 1–7. The initial solution contains a mixture of pseudoephedrine (50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and dextromethorphan (10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$).

additions of two analytes (PSU and DEX) in a certain ratio concentration into an unknown mixture. NAS vectors for components were calculated simultaneously based on eqs. (5), (6) and demonstrated in Figs. 4A and B respectively. Fig. 5 shows the norms of NAS vectors for analytes (PSU and DEX) versus standard added concentrations that could be used to calculate the simultaneous concentrations of each analyte respectively by interpolation.

Reagents :

Pseudoephedrine and dextromethorphan were kindly provided by Alborz Daroo Pharmaceutical Co. (Tehran, Iran). Analytical grade of phosphoric acid, boric acid, acetic acid and sodium hydroxide were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). All other reagents were of analytical grade.

Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffers (0.1 mol L^{-1} in phosphate, acetate and borate) in the pH range of 2–10 were used throughout.

A 1.0×10^{-3} mol L^{-1} pseudoephedrine hydrochloride solution was prepared daily by dissolving 0.0201 g of PSE (99.5%) in water and diluted in a 100 ml volumetric flask. These solutions were reserved in a refrigerator at 4 °C in dark. More dilute solutions were prepared by serial dilution with water. A 1.0×10^{-3} mol L^{-1} dextromethorphan solution was prepared daily by

dissolving 0.0352 g of DEX (99.5%) in water and diluted in a 100 ml volumetric flask. These solutions were reserved in a refrigerator at 4 °C in dark. More dilute solutions were prepared by serial dilution with water.

Instrumentation and software :

UV-Visible absorption spectra were measured on an Agilent UV-Vis spectrophotometer, Perkin-Elmer (Lambda 25), with the use of 1.0 cm quartz cells.

A Pentium IV (2.53 GHz) computer controlled all the setting and data processing. All spectra were saved in text files and transformed to an in house Matlab program version 7.6.0.324 (R2008a) to calculate the norm of NAS vectors.

A pH-meter (Metrohm, Model 827) with a double junction glass electrode was used to determine pH of the solutions.

Preparation of real samples :

To assay cough syrup containing pseudoephedrine (30 mg) and dextromethorphan (15 mg) in 5.0 mL syrup, *ca.* 5.0 mL of syrup was transferred into a 50-mL measuring flask and diluted to the mark by doubly distilled water. The absorbances of the solutions recorded after simultaneous standard additions of two analytes after 100 times more dilution.

Recommended procedure :

An aliquot of a solution containing PSU and/or DEX

Fig. 4. NAS curves for (A) pseudoephedrine and (B) dextromethorphan. All of the conditions are as Fig. 4.

Fig. 5. Norms of NASs for components PSU and DEX vs added concentrations. All of the conditions are as Fig. 4.

and 1.0 ml Britton-Robinson buffer solution (pH 9.0) were added into a 25 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with deionized water after simultaneous standard additions of two species (PSU and DEX) at the same molar ratio. The spectrum of each solution was recorded in the wavelength range of 220–300 nm and saved as text files. For calculating the norms of NAS vectors for each analyte, the matrixes of S and T designed according to the concentration ranges of Table 1 at the wavelength range of 220–300 nm. Then the text files related to each standard addition transferred to Matlab program for calculating the norms of PSU and DEX simultaneously (eqs. (5), (6)). In the end, the concentration of each component was calculated by standard addition plot (Norm of NAS vs added concentrations).

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of PSU and DEX under certain experimental conditions have shown in Fig. 2. As can be seen, the maximum wavelengths of two compounds are close to each other and their spectra overlapped. Therefore, determination of PSU and DEX in the presence of each other is impossible by classical spectrophotometry. Consequently, we used NASSAM as a chemometrics method to solve matrix effect and interferent errors simultaneously.

Effect of operational parameters :

In order to optimize the procedure for the simultaneous determination of pseudoephedrine and dextromethorphan, the effect of pH on the sensitivity and overlapping was studied. The absorbances at maximum wavelengths do not change significantly, and also the overlap between two species does not dependence to pH. Consequently, pH of 9.0 was selected as an optimum to obtain higher selectivity in the presence of cationic media.

In order to study the reproducibility of the proposed method at optimum pH, some synthetic mixtures containing PSU and DEX have been analysed several times (n = 4). The means of the calculated RSD (%) were 2.63 and 2.93% for pseudoephedrine and dextromethorphan respectively.

Analysis in some synthetic and real samples :

For showing the applicability of the proposed method

in the simultaneous determination of pseudoephedrine and dextromethorphan, standard concentrations of two appropriate compounds in some synthetic mixtures were determined simultaneously by NASSAM and the obtained results have shown in Table 3. Also, some pharmaceutical formulations (Pseudoephedrine-P syrup) manufactured by different pharmaceutical companies located in Iran have been analysed by the proposed method. As it has shown in Table 4, the results have validated with spiked standard solutions with superior consistency.

Table 3. Replicate determinations of PSU and DEX in some synthetic samples

Mixture	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)		Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)		RSD (%)	
	PSU	DEX	PSU	DEX	PSU	DEX
1	150.0	10.0	154.5	10.2	2.24	2.19
	150.0	10.0	157.0	10.2		
	150.0	10.0	162.5	10.5		
	150.0	10.0	160.5	10.4		
2	50.0	50.0	51.5	52.3	2.19	2.93
	50.0	50.0	51.5	51.2		
	50.0	50.0	53.5	50.2		
	50.0	50.0	53.5	48.8		
3	50.0	10.0	48.5	9.6	3.45	3.67
	50.0	10.0	52.5	9.8		
	50.0	10.0	51.5	9.5		
	50.0	10.0	50.0	9.0		

Table 4. Determination of PSU and DEX in some synthetic mixtures

Sample	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)		Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)		Recovery (%)	
	DEX	DEX	PSU	PSU	DEX	PSU
1	10	50	10.3	45.5	103.0	91.0
2	10	100	9.9	103.5	99.1	103.5
3	50	25	54.5	23.0	109.1	92.0
4	70	40	74.0	41.5	105.7	103.5
5	20	100	19.7	93.5	98.3	93.5
6	20	80	20.0	78.5	100.0	93.1
7	10	70	9.4	73.5	94.1	105.0
8	50	10	51.9	11.5	103.8	115.0
9	100	10	105.7	11.0	105.7	110.0
10	25	50	25.1	52.5	100.3	105.0
11	40	70	41.7	72.5	104.2	103.6
12	80	20	76.9	23.0	96.1	115.0
13	10	40	9.9	42.0	99.2	105.0
14	100	20	100.2	23.5	102.2	117.5

Table 5. Replicate measurements of PSU and DEX in some cough syrups, expressed as $\bar{X} \pm (tS.D.)/\sqrt{N}$, for $N = 3$ measurements and $t_{95\%, (N-1=2)} = 2.92$

Sample ^a	Added (mg)		Found (mg)		Recovery (%)	
	DEX	PSU	DEX	PSU	DEX	PSU
Brand I	-	-	15.22 ± 0.30	30.63 ± 0.65	101.46	101.00
	17.64	505.05	30.71 ± 0.45	532.80 ± 4.96	87.81	99.50
Brand II	-	-	14.96 ± 0.80	30.20 ± 0.31	97.93	100.60
	17.64	505.05	33.61 ± 1.90	527.77 ± 4.96	105.72	98.36
Brand III	-	-	14.34 ± 0.04	28.95 ± 0.65	95.60	96.50

^aBrands I to III are cold syrups manufactured by Alborz Daroo, Ramofarmin and Pursina Pharmaceutical Companies respectively. Each brand contains pseudoephedrine (30 mg) and dextromethorphan (15 mg) in each 5 ml of syrup.

Conclusion

Quantification of pseudoephedrine and dextromethorphan was accomplished from spectrophotometric data by a novel method based on the net analyte signal and standard addition of two analytes in a certain ratio concentration. When the interferents are known, the part of the overlapping spectra orthogonal to the space of interferents can be calculated as the net analyte signal and this is attributed to the analyte concentration. Therefore the analyte concentrations can be determined simultaneously from a unique standard addition plot. Two popular multivariate calibration methods, i.e. PCR and PLS, require that the optimum number of factors or principal components are selected. This selection may lead to overfitting and/or underfitting. In this study, a new analysis method that does not require factor selection has developed. The proposed method is useful for simultaneous determination of analytes in mixtures without the need for a prior separation or special conditions to resolve the spectra of analytes. The proposed method is simple, inexpensive, precise and affordable. It also requires no complex pre-treatment. Hence, it can be a powerful and substituted method in comparison with HPLC for analysis of pseudoephedrine and dextromethorphan syrups in the unit of quantitation control.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of this work by Islamic Azad University Branch of Gachsaran (IAUG) and the assistance of Alborz Daroo Pharmaceutical Co. for providing pure drugs.

References

1. M. M. Galera, D. P. Zamora, J. L. M. Vidal, A. G. Frenich, A. E. Mansilla, A. Munoz de la Pena and F. S. Lopez, *Talanta*, 2003, **59**, 1107.
2. M. Kompany-Zareha and S. Mirzaei, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **526**, 83.
3. B. Hemmateenejad, R. Ghavami, R. Miri and M. Shamsipur, *Talanta*, 2006, **68**, 1222.
4. A. Espinosa-Mansilla, I. Duran Meras, M. J. R. Gomez, Arsenio Munoz de la Pena and F. Salinas, *Talanta*, 2002, **58**, 255.
5. A. Mirmohseni, H. Abdollahi and K. Rostamizadeh, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2007, **585**, 179.
6. A. Munoz de la Pena, A. Espinosa-Mansilla, M. I. Acedo Valenzuela, H. C. Goicoechea and A. C. Olivieri, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2002, **463**, 75.
7. K. Asadpour-Zeynalnia and M. Bastami, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2010, **75**, 589.
8. P. L. Denniston (ed.), "Physicians GenRx", Denniston, Riverside, 1995, p. II-1686.
9. N. Wu, W. Feng, E. Lin, G. Chen, J. Patel, T. M. Chan and B. Pramanik, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2002, **30**, 1143.
10. S. N. Makhija and P. R. Vavia, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2001, **25**, 663.
11. H. Mahgoub, A. A. Gazy, F. A. El-Yazbi, M. A. El-Sayed and R. M. Youssef, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2003, **31**, 801.
12. F. Onur, C. Yucesoy, S. Dermis, M. Kartal and G. Kkdil, *Talanta*, 2000, **51**, 269.
13. M. M. Mabrouk, H. M. El-Fatratry, S. Hammad and A. A. M. Wahbi, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2003, **33**, 597.
14. J. E. F. Reynolds, "Martindale The Extra Pharmacopoeia", 31st ed., Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1993.
15. J. P. Rauha, H. Salomies and M. Aalto, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1996, **15**, 287.

16. H. P. Hendrickson, B. J. Gurley and W. D. Wessinger, *J. Chromatogr. (B)*, 2003, **788**, 261.
17. S. S. Vengurlekar, J. Heitkamp, F. McCush, P. R. Velagaleti, J. H. Brisson and S. L. Bramer, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2002, **30**, 113.
18. C. V. Tantishaiyakul, P. Poeaknapo, K. Sribun and J. Sirisuppanon, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1998, **17**, 237.
19. A. R. Lee and T. M. Hu, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1994, **12**, 747.
20. M. R. Gomez, R. A. Olsina, L. D. Martinez and M. F. Silva, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2002, **30**, 791.
21. X. Xu and J. T. Stewart, *J. Liq. Chromatogr. Related Technol.*, 2000, **23**, 1.
22. A. Lorber, *Anal. Chem.*, 1986, **58**, 1167.